

Influences on Deliberation Quality: Exploring How Question Characteristics Affect Scientific Deliberation

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ABSTRACT

This study analyzes the characteristics of questions asked on social question-and-answer (Q&A) sites and explores how the characteristics of those questions affect deliberation quality. We collected COVID-19 virus discussions from an English (Quora) and a Chinese (Zhihu) social Q&A site. Content analysis found that certain question characteristics (i.e., length, type, emotion) significantly influenced user engagement and content quality. Longer questions were more likely to trigger answers with higher user engagement yet lower content quality. Conversational questions tended to develop answers with a higher engagement level, while informational questions were more likely to lead to higher content quality and more diverse content. Neutral questions might trigger higher user engagement level and higher rationality. Cross-platform and cross-culture aspects are also discussed.

KEYWORDS

Social Q&A; Online Deliberation; Scientific Controversy

INTRODUCTION

Online deliberation is a type of public online discussion regarding sociopolitical problems; this offers equal opportunities for the public to participate and share various opinions and perspectives (Baek, Wojcieszak, & Delli Carpini, 2012). Engaging in online deliberation helps develop awareness of the reasons behind different views, potentially increases political engagement, and promotes general community participation (Cappella, Price, & Nir, 2002; Price & Cappella, 2002). We presume that people can benefit more from engaging in high-quality deliberations; therefore, this study attempts to examine the impact factor on deliberation quality and recommend strategies to promote high-quality deliberation.

We conducted this study on social Q&A platforms, as more knowledge sharing occurs on these platforms than other social network sites (Guan, Wang, Jin, & Song, 2018) and because people tend to share more thought-provoking opinions about society on these sites. Additionally, we believe discussions on social Q&A platforms fit the definition of online deliberation better. Thus, we collected discussions on social Q&A platforms and evaluated online deliberation quality by assessing the answers on each platform. Because COVID-19 (hereby COVID) is a relatively new scientific topic and we know little about the discussion characteristics of this topic, we chose this topic with the hopes that this study's results can contribute to providing a better understanding of how people engage in COVID-related discussions.

We sampled data from two social Q&A platforms. One, Quora, is a dominant U.S. platform, and one of the most popular social Q&A sites in the U.S. The other, Zhihu, is a popular Chinese equivalent of Quora. Since COVID is a scientific topic with worldwide implications, it proved to be salient for comparing online discussions in countries with differing cultural backgrounds and attitudes towards dealing with COVID.

RELATED RESEARCH

Prior studies have identified that question characteristics can affect the quality of answers on social Q&A platforms. However, research on how question type influences answer quality has mixed results. Harper et al. (2009; 2008; 2010) classified social Q&A questions into two distinct types: conversational and informational. Conversational questions are more likely to predict high-quality answers, measured by longer answer length. Zhao et al. (2021) applied the same classification promoted by Harper et al. (2008) to examine the impact of a question's characteristics on answer outcomes; they identified contradictory findings, stating that on average, answer length for informational questions is longer than that for conversational questions. Additionally, they found that conversational questions received higher levels of user engagement.

This study's quality evaluation framework is based on various studies which theorized answer quality criteria on social Q&A platforms (see Table 2). Relevance was measured to identify whether a discussion was regarding the initial topic (Janssen & Kies, 2005); the higher the score was, the more related the answers were to the original questions. Diversity was based on whether the answers provided abundant and comprehensive contents (Stromer-Galley, 2007); higher scores indicate more diverse answers. Civility was measured to see whether participants interacted with each other politely and with mutual respect (Papacharissi, 2004); higher scores indicated more politeness. Rationality was measured by examining whether the participants supported their arguments with reasoned, valid claims (Jurgen Habermas & Habermas, 1991); the higher the scores were, the more rationality was

observed in answers. Additionally, user engagement criteria (e.g., number of votes and number of likes) were also used in measuring answer quality (Zhao et al., 2021).

In summary, as previous studies have mixed results on how question characteristics affect answer quality, there is a need to examine it under our research setting. Additionally, most of the prior research only examined various topics and questions on social Q&A platforms, instead of focusing on scientific topics. Finally, cross-cultural and cross-platform research on this research topic is rare; this research will address these literature gaps.

METHOD

Data Collection

We harvested questions and answers on Zhihu at the early stage of COVID (from January to March 2020) using a web crawler, and manually collected data from Quora later. Question data included question title, number of answers, and question URL. After removing questions without answers, we obtained 607 questions from Zhihu and 81 questions from Quora.

After all questions were acquired, we randomly sampled 20 questions that had more than five answers from each platform and used the crawler to randomly collect five answers from each question, resulting in 100 answers from each platform. The data types we collected included text content, length of the text, number of votes, and number of comments.

Data Analysis

We used question categories from prior studies (Bodoff & Raban, 2016; F Maxwell Harper et al., 2009; F. Maxwell Harper et al., 2008; F Maxwell Harper et al., 2010; Zhao et al., 2021) and added some new characteristics from observing our data. We primarily focused on three characteristics: length, type, and emotion (see Table 1). Question length, measuring by word count, would reveal whether elaborating on questions would have made any difference (Liu & Zhang, 2020). Question types would show how the information-seeking intention influenced the deliberation quality. We also examined how the open or closed nature of a question influenced deliberation quality, and how the emotion contained in the question influenced quality.

Categories		Definition	Example
Length		Number of words.	
Type	Informational	Ask for data, information, knowledge.	Are all public servants vaccinated in China?
	Conversational	Try to build up relationship with others, ask questions about personal experiences.	For those who get the COVID vaccine, how do you guys feel about it?
Emotion	Negative	Contain negative emotion words.	As a nurse, which side of the COVID experience are you on? I've seen videos of nurses saying it's awful and traumatizing, and nurses saying their hospitals are empty, numbers are manipulated, and things are overblown. I don't know what to think.
	Neutral	Do not contain negative or positive emotion, staying in neutral.	Those who have had COVID already, how quickly did you start experiencing symptoms after being exposed? Did the symptoms show up suddenly?
	Positive	Contain positive emotion words.	No examples available.

Table 1. Question Type Taxonomy

To analyze answers, we measured the deliberation quality from two aspects: user engagement and the content quality evaluation (see Table 2). User engagement was identified by the number of votes, number of comments, and answer length. We also scored each answer from one to five points according to a four-dimensional content quality evaluation framework (Jurgen Habermas & Habermas, 1991; Janssen & Kies, 2005; Papacharissi, 2004; Stromer-Galley, 2007).

User engagement	
Voter	Number of voters.
Comment	Number of comments.
Answer length	Length of each answer (Halpern & Gibbs, 2013).
Content quality	
Civility	Participants interact with each other politely and with mutual respect (Papacharissi, 2004).
Relevance	Participants discuss around initial topics (Janssen & Kies, 2005).
Rationality	Participants support their statements with reasoned validity claims (Jurgen Habermas & Habermas, 1991; Jürgen Habermas, McCarthy, & McCarthy, 1984).
Diversity	There are participants in the dialogue with distinct views on a particular issue (Stromer-Galley, 2007).

Table 2. Deliberation Quality Evaluation

In order to test intercoder reliability, two researchers rated 10% of the answers separately. After reaching moderate intercoder reliability (Kappa result: 0.41-0.60) (McHugh, 2012), one of the researchers rated the rest of the answers. For the Zhihu answers, the Kappa value is 0.57, whereas for Quora, the Kappa value is 0.54. The Kappa values indicated that intercoder reliabilities were generally sufficient to proceed with the analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Question Characteristics vs User Engagement

We applied Independent-Sample T to examine the content quality difference between Quora and Zhihu (see Table 3). The Zhihu discussions had a significantly higher number of voters and comments than Quora ($M=1630.78$ vs. $M=97.89$, $p<.001$; $M=155.95$ vs $M=10.09$, $p<.001$); regarding COVID discussions, Zhihu had more user interactions than Quora.

		Vote	Comment	Answer length
Platform	Quora	97.89	10.09	525.48
	Zhihu	1630.78***	155.95***	660.94
Length		.258**	.192**	-.167*
Type	Informational	249.87	56.24	536.85
	Conversational	1318.5*	102.82	634.87
Emotion	Negative	198.43	198.43	451.69
	Neutral	1005.59	1005.59	623.23
Sig. (*<.05; **<.01; ***<.001)				

Table 3. Question Characteristics vs. User Engagement

By applying the Pearson Correlation Coefficient test, we found that questions with longer titles might trigger more votes and more comments, which implies that longer titles tend to trigger more user interaction (see Table 3). However, a longer question title predicts a shorter answer length. This finding is in contrast with previous studies, which show longer initial posts are correlated with longer replies (Liu & Zhang, 2020). Our interpretation is that longer questions tend to be more specific and users may insist on specific criteria (Bodoff & Raban, 2016).

We applied the Independent-Sample T test to examine the user engagement difference between different question types (see Table 3). Conversational questions had significantly more voters than informational questions ($M = 1318.5$ vs. $M = 249.87$, $p < .05$). Zhao et al. (2021) agreed with this result. Conversational questions, which often promote discussion, are subjective views or feelings which might more easily generate “internal echoes” with others.

We did not find any positive questions in our dataset. Understandably, happy emotions decreased and sadness increased in the early stage of COVID outbreak (Meléndez et al., 2020; Rossell et al., 2021). However, the emotions seem not to significantly influence user engagement, as we can see in Table 3.

Question Characteristics vs Answer Quality Score

In general, there is a significant difference between Quora and Zhihu regarding content quality (see Table 4). Zhihu had a significant higher quality score than Quora in rationality and average score. The Chinese government has implemented more sophisticated Internet content control (King, Pan, & Roberts, 2013, 2014), which may have caused people to restrain expressing negative emotions (i.e., less rationality) regarding COVID. It is possible that people's concerns towards censorship may have influenced their behaviors (Zhang, Tandoc Jr, & Han, 2022; Zhu & Fu, 2021) and to be cautious about their online expressions.

		Relevance	Diversity	Civility	Rationality	Average
Platform	Quora	3.70*	2.64***	2.84***	2.32	2.88
	Zhihu	3.68	2.61	2.71	3.33**	3.08**
Length		-0.106	-.210**	-0.093	0.057	-0.119
Type	Informational	3.71*	2.79*	2.79	2.92	3.05
	Conversational	3.68	2.50	2.77	2.76	2.93
Emotion	Negative	3.57	2.66	2.86	2.40	2.87
	Neutral	3.72	2.62	2.76	2.92**	3.00

Sig. (*<.05; **<.01; ***<.001)

Table 4. Question Characteristics vs. Answer Quality Score

Length also significantly influenced the diversity ($r = -.210, p < .01$) of the answer contents (see Table 4). The longer the question titles were, the less diverse the answers became. This result corresponds with the finding in the previous section of this study where longer question titles result in a shorter answer length. It is likely that longer titles may have provided more detailed descriptions and clearer directions for the answers. Thus, users might have focused on specific aspects when answering questions and narrowed down the breadth of their answers.

Informational questions scored higher than conversational questions ($M = 3.71$ vs. $M = 3.68, p < .05$; $M = 2.79$ vs. $M = 2.50, p < .05$) regarding relevance and diversity (see Table 4). This could be due to conversational questions being more likely to promote discussion, with most users answering questions egocentrically and focusing on personal experiences, sharing, or emotional abreaction.

Neutral questions had significantly higher scores in rationality (Mean = 2.92, Sig. < .001) than negative questions ($M = 2.40, p < .001$), and it showed that neutral questions might have received more answers with higher rationale.

CONCLUSION

In this study, we provided evidence of how question characteristics influenced the quality of answers and compared how results differed across U.S.-based Quora and China-based Zhihu. We found that Zhihu has significant higher user engagement level and answer quality than Quora overall. We speculated that stricter content censorship might be a factor, which to some extent maintained a rational discussion environment towards COVID. The length of the question title, type of the question, and emotion of the question would significantly affect user engagement and content quality. We inferred that shorter questions are more ambiguous and would inspire answers with more diverse aspects and opinions. Informational questions (i.e., more factual) were more likely to trigger subtopics within the answers, while answers to conversational questions were more monotonic about personal experience or emotional support. Additionally, we found neutral questions were more likely to have answers with higher rationality. Therefore, in order to get higher-quality answers, we recommend using a neutral tone to express questions, as using negative emotions in questions might lead to lower content quality of answers in this context where a contended scientific topic was the focus. We believe that this study also contributes to social Q&A research from a cross-cultural and cross-platform perspective.

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